

Characterisation of Methyl Viologen Radical Cation in Aqueous Organic Mixed Solvent System : A Pulse Radiolysis Study

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The spectroscopic characteristics and one-electron reduction potential (E^1) of methyl viologen in aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone solvent have been investigated by pulse radiolysis technique. The E^1 is independent of pH within the range 6–12. The possibility of dimer radical formation has been ruled out from the experimental evidence. On the basis of our result, the E^1 values for several quinone-semiquinone systems have been corrected.

Methyl viologen (I : MV^{2+}), popularly known as paraquat, chemically 1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium dichloride (or sulphate), is well-known for its herbicidal and toxicological activities¹⁻³. MV^{2+} is also a well-known electron acceptor and an important component in various photochemical and photoelectrochemical cells for the utilisation of solar energy⁴. The formation and reactivity of the one-electron reduced cation $MV^{\bullet+}$ (II) has been extensively studied⁵⁻⁸.

The electron addition reaction has been shown by pulse radiolysis to be very efficient, with reported rate constant of 7×10^{10} (Ref. 9) to 8.4×10^{10} $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ (Refs. 10, 11). However, the molar extinction coefficient values at the two absorption peaks of 395 and 600 nm in aqueous solution differ widely, ranging from 10000¹² to 13700¹³

$\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 600 nm and from 33000⁹ to 45000¹³ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 395 nm. A $\text{p}K_a$ of 2.9 ± 0.1 has also been reported⁷ for the radical cation $MV^{\bullet+}$.

In course of our work in pulse radiolysis of substituted quinones in mixed aqueous organic solvent comprising of 5 mol dm^{-3} isopropyl alcohol and 1 mol dm^{-3} acetone in water and also in pure water containing 10^{-1} mol dm^{-3} sodium formate, differences were observed in the redox characteristics of $MV^{\bullet+}$ in the two media. Since MV^{2+} has been used universally by many laboratories as a redox reference, an accurate value of the one-electron reduction potential (E^1) is absolutely essential. Though the E^1 ($MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}$) is well estimated in aqueous solvent, the value is not accurately known in aqueous organic solvent except that Ledwith¹⁴ and Wardman and Clarke¹⁵ have shown that the E^1 value of the $MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}$ couple in aqueous alcoholic solvents will be more positive than E^1 in water. In order to remove ambiguities, we have extensively studied the characteristics of $MV^{\bullet+}$ in the aqueous formate and in aqueous organic mixed solvent. A number of E^1 values hitherto reported for different systems in mixed aqueous organic solvent¹⁶⁻¹⁸ have also been corrected.

Results and Discussion

Mixed aqueous organic solvent, comprising of

5 mol dm⁻³ isopropyl alcohol and 1 mol dm⁻³ acetone in water, offers a unique solvent system for radiation chemical reduction of substrates insoluble or very sparingly soluble in water or aqueous solvent systems. The molarities of isopropyl alcohol and acetone in the mixed solvent systems are important since, as a result of the primary radiation chemical reactions, the exclusive reducing agent turns out to be the isopropyl alcohol radical or acetone ketyl radical (CH₃C[•]OHCH₃), as follows :

Another advantage of this solvent system is that measurement of pH is still significant¹⁶⁻¹⁸, since the solvent systems contains > 30 mol dm⁻³ water, i.e. is predominantly aqueous. Insoluble substrates like quinizarin (1,4-dihydroxy-9,10-anthraquinone) or other anthraquinone derivatives can be readily solubilised and studied¹⁶⁻¹⁸ in this solvent system.

In aqueous formate (10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³) solution, reaction (1) is followed by reaction (5) as follows :

When electron pulses are delivered to a nitrogen-bubbled dilute aqueous organic solution of MV²⁺ (~10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³), containing 5 mol dm⁻³ isopropyl alcohol and 1 mol dm⁻³ acetone, the principal interaction of radiation occurs with water (major component, reaction 1), followed by reactions (2) to (4) to produce (CH₃)₂C[•]OH radical, which in turn reduces MV²⁺ to MV^{•+} (reaction 6),

In aqueous 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ formate solution (N₂-bubbled), the corresponding reactions are

Fig. 1. MV^{•+}-MV²⁺ difference absorption spectra in aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone solution; dose ~5 Gy : (●) pH 1.5 and (○) pH 8.

The differences between the optical densities of the free radical MV^{•+} and the parent MV²⁺ were measured several microseconds after giving electron pulses to N₂-bubbled solutions containing MV²⁺. The spectra at pH 1.5 and 8.0 obtained in aqueous organic mixed solvent are shown in Fig. 1. It is evident from the figure that there is no observable difference between the spectra. In fact it has been observed that the system gives the same difference spectra between pH 1.5 and 12, clearly showing that there is no intervening pK_a within this pH range. Same experiment was repeated in aqueous solution containing 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ sodium formate. Again, a qualitatively similar spectrum was obtained within the pH range 1.5-12. This result clearly shows that the pK_a of 2.9 ± 0.1 as reported earlier⁷ was a wrong conclusion. Thus MV^{•+} exists in only one form in the pH range 1.5-12.

A G-value (number of molecules formed or decomposed on absorption of 100 eV of radiation; or, in SI units, number of moles formed or decomposed on absorption of 1 J of radiation, 1 eV = 1.602 × 10⁻¹⁹ J) of 6.2 molecules (100 eV)⁻¹ c. 6.42

$\times 10^{-7} \text{ mol J}^{-1}$ ($1 \text{ mol J}^{-1} = 9.65 \times 10^6 \text{ molecules (100 eV)}^{-1}$), was assumed for the reducing radicals in the mixed solvent system¹⁶⁻¹⁸, leaving provision for the unreactive β -isopropyl radical, $\text{C}^\bullet\text{H}_2\text{CHOHCH}_3$, compared to 6.5 molecules $(100 \text{ eV})^{-1}$ in aqueous formate solutions¹⁹. This G -value was confirmed by comparing the transient absorption spectrum obtained from methyl-1,4-benzoquinone in aqueous formate and aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone systems at pH 7.

There was a small amount of parent (MV^{2+}) absorption in the uv-end of the spectrum. Thus the spectra in Fig. 1 were corrected for parent depletion, using the expression,

$$\epsilon_R^\lambda = \epsilon_p^\lambda + \frac{\text{OD} \times 2.9 \times 7.1 \times 10^3}{\text{OD}(\text{SCN})_2^{\bullet-} \times 6.2} \quad (9)$$

where, the value of G for $(\text{SCN})_2^{\bullet-}$ is 2.9 molecules $(100 \text{ eV})^{-1}$ (i.e. $3.1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol J}^{-1}$) and the extinction coefficient of $(\text{SCN})_2^{\bullet-}$ at 500 nm is $7.1 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Here, ϵ_p is the extinction coefficient of MV^{2+} at the corresponding wavelength. The corrected absorption spectra of $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ in aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone solvent at pH 1.5 and 8.0 are given in Fig. 2. One observes that at both the pH the spectra are identical, with the strong 395 nm peak having an extinction coefficient

Fig. 2. Corrected absorption spectrum of $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ in aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone solution: (●) pH 1.5 and (○) 8.

of $39000 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the broad 610 nm peak having an extinction coefficient of $\sim 12000 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, values very close to those reported^{9,12,13} for aqueous systems.

In order to ensure that no dimer radicals are formed, uv-visible absorption spectra of $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ were measured at variable radiation doses (to vary the amount of $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ formed) and at variable MV^{2+} concentration. There was no observed difference in the normalised spectra obtained at different doses and also the spectra obtained at varied MV^{2+} concentrations. Thus, the possibility of formation of a dimer radical ($\text{MV}^{2+} \dots \text{MV}^{\bullet+}$) or a diradical $(\text{MV}^{\bullet+})_2$ was ruled out. On plotting OD at λ_{max} as a function of dose (Gray), a straight-line plot was obtained as shown in Fig. 3. On plotting OD at λ_{max} as

Fig. 3. Variation of absorption of $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ at 395 nm with radiation dose.

a function of $[\text{MV}^{2+}]$, a straight-line parallel to $[\text{MV}^{2+}]$ axis was obtained (Fig. 4). On plotting the rate of growth of the $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ absorption signal as a function of $[\text{MV}^{2+}]$, a straight-line passing through the origin was obtained (Fig. 5), clearly showing that the formation of $\text{MV}^{\bullet+}$ is a simple process without any measurable secondary process. Based on these data, the possibility of a dimer formation was ruled out.

The changing of the solvent from pure water

Fig. 4. Variation of absorption of MV^{•+} at 395 nm with MV²⁺ concentration.

to aqueous organic mixtures with isopropyl alcohol and acetone will have a drastic effect in the solvation characteristics of the ions and consequently on their redox characteristics. The effect of added organic solvents on the redox equilibria for MV²⁺/MV^{•+} can be understood in terms of solvation equilibria originally proposed by Kosower and Cotter¹² to explain the shift in frequency of the charge transfer

Fig. 5. Variation of formation rate constant of MV^{•+} with MV²⁺ concentration.

transition of MV²⁺ with changing solvents, arising directly from the Franck-Condon principle. MV²⁺ will be much more favourably solvated by water than MV^{•+}. Similarly, alcohol or acetone will preferentially solvate MV^{•+} rather than MV²⁺. Thus on changing the solvent from pure water to progressively less aqueous type aqueous organic solvents, the solvation energy of MV²⁺ will decrease and that of MV^{•+} will simultaneously increase. Consequently, there will be a progressive decrease in the free energy difference between MV²⁺ and MV^{•+} on changing the solvent from aqueous to less aqueous environments. This should result in a more positive value of the one-electron reduction potential (E^1) in aqueous organic solvent than that, i.e. -450 mV at pH 7, in aqueous solution¹³, for the system MV²⁺/MV^{•+}.

On delivery of an electron pulse of low dose (about 5 Gy, to minimise radical-radical reactions) to a N₂-bubbled solution containing MV²⁺ and a suitable redox reference (R), an electron transfer equilibrium is readily established as follows :

9,10-Anthraquinone-2-sulphonate (AQS) and duroquinone (DQ : 2,3,5,6-tetramethyl-1,4-benzoquinone) were chosen as redox reference standards. E^1 for AQS has been shown¹⁵ to be independent of solvent composition when alcohol is added to water. E^1 for AQS in aqueous organic mixed solvent was accordingly taken as -380 mV at 25°. On setting up a redox equilibrium between AQS and DQ in the mixed solvent as well as in aqueous formate solution,

it was first established that the E^1 of DQ (-240 mV at pH 7)¹⁹ is also independent of solvent composition as in the case of AQS. Fig. 6 shows the redox equilibration between the system AQS/AQS^{•-} and MV²⁺/MV^{•+} in aqueous organic mixed solvent (Fig. 6.I) and in aqueous formate (Fig. 6.II) at pH ~ 11. It is very clear from Fig. 6 that the redox process in the two cases

Fig.6. Oscilloscopic traces showing attainment of electron-transfer equilibrium in (I) aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone and (II) aqueous formate solutions; $\lambda = 610$ nm, Dose ~ 5 Gy: (A) $MV^{\bullet+}$ alone, (B) $AQS^{\bullet-}$ alone and (C) $MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}$ and $AQS/AQS^{\bullet-}$ equilibrium system; IC: $[MV^{2+}] = 4.1 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} and $[AQS] = 7.08 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} ; IIC: $[MV^{2+}] = 4.27 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} and $[AQS] = 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} .

are different. While in aqueous solvent, the electron transfer takes place,

from left to right of the equation (12), in the aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone solvent, it takes place from the right to the left. By varying the concentrations of MV^{2+} and AQS suitably, it was possible to establish electron transfer equilibrium as in equation (12). Although 395 nm is a better wavelength for any such redox experiment due to

higher extinction coefficient of $MV^{\bullet+}$, we repeated the experiments at both 395 and 610 nm since at 610 nm, $MV^{\bullet+}$ is the only absorbing species, giving better accuracy. A set of results at 610 nm is shown in Fig. 6. The equilibrium constant (K) was obtained by measurement of the equilibrium optical densities, and defined as

$$K = \frac{[AQS] [MV^{\bullet+}]}{[AQS^{\bullet-}] [MV^{2+}]} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{also, } E(MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}) = E(AQS/AQS^{\bullet-}) + 59 \log K \quad (14)$$

$$= -380 + 59 \log K \quad (15)$$

By performing a careful series of experiments within the pH 6–12 and varying the concentrations of AQS and MV^{2+} between 1×10^{-4} and 2×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} , a value of $E_7^1 = -330$ mV has been established for the couple $MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}$, compared to $E_7^1 = -450$ mV in aqueous formate solution. The same results were obtained on replacing AQS with DQ as a redox reference.

Fig. 7 shows a plot of $E^1(MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+})$ vs pH

Fig. 7. Constancy of E^1 vs pH for $MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}$ in aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone solvent.

in the aqueous organic mixed solvent. Within experimental error, the points lie around a straight-line parallel to the pH-axis, showing again that $MV^{\bullet+}$ does not undergo any dimerisation, and more im-

portant, there is no likely pK_a of $MV^{\bullet+}$ as stipulated earlier⁷.

Based on the present results, we are in a position to correct the values of a large number of E^1 values reported by us earlier on the basis of $E^1 = -350$ mV, adopted for $MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}$ system in aqueous-organic mixed solvent, following Ledwith¹⁴ and Wardman and Clarke¹⁵. Table 1 gives a compilation of the corrected E^1 values (and wherever possible, E^2 , the second one-electron reduction potential and E^m , the two-electron reduction potential values) for some quinone/semiquinone systems in aqueous isopropyl alcohol-acetone solvent.

TABLE 1—CORRECTED VALUES OF E^1 , E^2 AND E^m FOR SUBSTITUTED QUINONE/SEMIQUINONE SYSTEMS, BASED ON $E^1(MV^{2+}/MV^{\bullet+}) = -330$ mV AT 25°

Quinone*	Earlier potential values (mV)			Corrected potential values based on this report (mV)		
	E^1	E^2	E^m	E^1	E^2	E^m
Quinizarin ^a	-269	-188	-229	-249	-168	-209
Quinizarin-2-sulphonate ^a	-298	-216	-257	-278	-196	-237
5-Methoxy-quinizarin ^a	-333	-192	-263	-313	-172	-243
1-Amino-4-hydroxy-AQ ^b	-428	-348	-388	-408	-328	-368
1,4-Diamino-AQ ^b	-430	-329	-380	-410	-309	-360
1,5-Dihydroxy-AQ ^c	-326	-273	-300	-306	-253	-280
1,8-Dihydroxy-AQ ^c	-345	-415	-380	-325	-395	-360

*AQ : 9,10-anthraquinone; quinizarin: 1,4-dihydroxy-9,10-anthraquinone. ^aRef. 18. ^bRef. 16. ^cRef. 17.

Experimental

All quinones (Aldrich) were purified by repeated recrystallisation from suitable solvents. All other chemicals were of the purest form available (Fluka, E. Merck or B.D.H.) and were used as such. Methyl viologen from three different sources were used: Aldrich, Sigma and Tokyo Kasei Kogyo (Japan), for comparison purpose. 70% $HClO_4$ and pure NaOH were used for making solutions acidic or alkaline. Triple-distilled water, along with spectroscopic grade (Spectrochem, India) acetone and isopropyl alcohol, were used for making solutions, which were buffered

with phosphate buffer wherever necessary. Nitrogen (IOLAR grade from Indian Oxygen Ltd.) was flushed for about 10 min through the solutions for deoxygenation purpose.

Details of the pulse radiolysis arrangements were as described earlier²⁰. A Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer was used for the ground state absorption measurements. An Orion 901A ionalyser fitted with a combination electrode was used for pH measurements. Absorbed radiation dose was measured by thiocyanate dosimetry^{21,22} (5×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} air-saturated KSCN) following the optical density of $(SCN)_2^{\bullet-}$ radicals at 500 nm produced under an isodose condition.

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